

New additions to the Indian flora in 2015

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The present paper enumerates the new discoveries of plants (except microbes) during 2015 from the political boundary of India. The group wise count of the current status of plants in India is given in an updated table. Some of these new discoveries can be of horticultural, agricultural and medicinal value in future.

Key Words: New discoveries; India; Seed plants; Fern; Bryophytes; Pteridophytes; Fungi; Algae.

Introduction:

Documentation and wholesome knowledge on plant diversity is essential to promote and enhance the ecosystem functions and derive benefits essential for human well-being including our cultural heritage. Research in plant taxonomy has taken a huge stride both in the field and in laboratories. Dissemination of knowledge, promotion of research in plant diversity is one of the major objectives in achieving the Aichi Biodiversity Targets. Botanical Survey of India has been taking a lead in research in plant taxonomy and to disseminate the information on new discoveries of plants within the political boundary of our country, otherwise scattered in vast array of journals published from different parts of world. This information has been catering the growing needs of updating our knowledge on biodiversity and the species count of our country. The present paper provides the details of new genera, species and new distributional records reported from India during the calendar year 2015. The genera, species and infra-specific taxa are arranged alphabetically with original citation followed by the family in parenthesis and its distribution.

An analysis of new discoveries of plants in India during 2015 revealed that seed plants and fungi discoveries were contributed by 60 per cent, while algae, bryophytes, and lichens together contribute rest 40 per cent of plant species. We have marked an increasing trend of taxonomic research in the field of lower plants in the current year. During the year 2015, out of 371 total discoveries, 269 taxa of non-vascular plants were added to the India flora, which is the highest in last nine years.

Current status of Plants in India

In the present state of our knowledge, India has 48,158 already identified plant species which needs to be updated every year with continuous efforts of discovery of new taxa. The group wise status of species recorded from India is given below:

Table 1: Group wise occurrence of plant species in India

Group	No. of species in India	Percentage of Indian Flora
Bacteria	1,120	2.34
Algae	7,331	15.23
Fungi	15,053	31.29
Lichens	2,479	5.15
Bryophytes	2,550	5.20
Pteridophytes	1,288	2.68
Gymnosperms	78	0.17
Angiosperms	18,259	37.94
TOTAL	48,158	100

During the year 2015, 12 new genera, 183 new species, 03 subspecies and 07 new varieties were discovered as new to science, while 01 genus, 144 species, 04 subspecies and 13 varieties were reported as new plant records for India. Among the new discoveries, fungi contributed the maximum with 32 per cent followed by seed plants accounted for 28 per cent, microbes with 13 percent, lichens with 12 percent, algae with 06 per cent, bryophytes with 05 per cent; fern and fern allies contributed the least with 04 per cent of the total discoveries. During 2015, new discoveries were reported from almost all the phytogeographic regions in which maximum discoveries were made from Eastern Himalaya (19%) followed by Western Ghat (18%), Andaman & Nicobar group of islands(15%), Northern Plains

(11%), Western Himalayas (10%), Eastern Ghats and North East Ranges (07%), Eastern Plains (05%), Deccan and Central highlands (03%) and Western Plains (02%). It is interesting to note that vascular plants contribute 31 per cent of the total discoveries while the non-vascular plants contribute 69 per cent of which fungi alone represents highest percentage (47%). It is also interesting to mention that, 13 wild species of balsam germplasm, 3 species of wild gingers, 3 species of figs, 6 species of sedges, 5 species of grasses, 1 species of cycad, and 36 species of wild mushrooms are discovered during 2015.

Fig.1 Percentage of discoveries made in different group during 2015

Fig.2 Percentage of Plant Discoveries made during 2015 from different physiogeographic Zones

ENUMERATION OF NEW GENERA, SPECIES AND INFRA-SPECIFIC TAXA SEED PLANTS

New Genera

Himgiria Pusalkar & D.K.Singh, J.Jap. Bot. 90:86.2015(CARYOPHYLLACEAE).

Distribution: Lahul-Spiti Division, Himachal Pradesh, India

Plectoglossa (Hook.f.)K.Prasad & Venu, Rheede 25(2):86.2015(ORCHIDACEAE).

Distribution: Nilgiri Hills, Western Ghats

Shivparvatia Pusalkar & D.K. Singh, J. Jap. Bot. 90: 81. 2015 (CARYOPHYLLACEAE).

Distribution: Trans Himalaya and Tibetan plateau region, India

New Species

Amaranthus parganensis Saubhik Das, Novon 23 : 406.2015(AMARANTHACEAE).

Distribution: EM Bypass, Kolkata, India

Anisochillus shoalamudianus Sunil & Naveen Kum., Webbia 70(2): 217. 2015(LAMIACEAE).

Distribution: Shoolamudi, Edamalayar Forest Range, Ernakulam District, Kerala, India, at 1216m altitude.

Aponogeton nateshii S.R. Yadav, Rheede 25 (1): 09.2015 (APONOGETONACEAE).

Distribution: Karel, Rajapur, Ratnagiri district of Maharashtra, India.

Bambusa mompaeana Naithani, Indian For. 141(5): 587.2015 (POACEAE).

Distribution: Warzong, 13 km after Bomdila, West Kameng district of Arunachal Pradesh, India, at 1600m altitude

Boesenbergia meghalayensis Aishwarya & M.Sabu, Phytotaxa 197(3): 186. 2015 (ZINGIBERACEAE).

Distribution: Nortiang road side, Shillong, Meghalaya, India at 1120m altitude.

Bulbophyllum chyrmangensis D.Verma, S.Lavana & Sushil K.Singh, Phytotaxa 195(1): 094.2015 (ORCHIDACEAE).

Distribution: Chyrman sacred groove, West Jaintia Hills District of Meghalaya, India.

Carex kotagirica A. Maji & V.P. Prasad, Rheede 25(2):81.2015 (CYPERACEAE).

Distribution: Nilgiri Hills, way to Kotagiri, Nilgiri District of Tamil Nadu, India.

Christisoniatomentosa J. Mathew & Kad. V. George, Webbia 70(2): 227. 2015 (OROBANCHACEAE).

Distribution: Vellakkaltheri, Kollam district, southern Western Ghats, Kerala, India, at 1800m altitude.

Cinnamomum agasthyamalyanum Robi, Sujanapal & Udayan, Inter. J. Adv. Res. 2(10):1012.2014 (LAURACEAE).

Distribution: Agasthyamala, of Kerala at 850m altitude.

Clausena agasthyamalyana E. S. S. Kumar, Shareef, Roy & Veldkamp, Nordic J. Bot. 33(2):151.2015. (RUTACEAE).

Distribution: Agasthyamala Biosphere Reserve of Kerala, India, at 1440m altitude.

Commelina badamica Nandikar & Gurav, Telopia 18:513. 2015 (COMMELINACEAE).

Distribution: Badami, Bagalkot District of Karnataka, India at 670m altitude.

Cycas pschannae R.C. Srivast.& Lalji Singh, Int. J. Curr. Res. Biosci. Plant Biol. 2(8):35. 2015 (CYCADACEAE).

Distribution: AJC Bose Indian Botanic Garden, Howrah, West Bengal, India.

Cyperus coonoorensis Viji, Pandur, Deepu & G.C. Tucker, Phytotaxa 203(2): 178. 2015 (CYPERACEAE).

Distribution: Coonoor, Nilgiri District of Tamil Nadu, India, at 1501m altitude.

Dimeria raviana Kiran Raj & Sivadasan, Phytotaxa 195(2):193.2015 (POACEAE).

Distribution: Periyar Tiger Reserve, Idukki District of Kerala, India.

Diospyros udaiyana P.S. Udayan, Bangladesh J. Plant Taxon. 22(2): 83. 2015 (EBENACEAE).

Distribution: Kakkayam, Malabar Wildlife Sanctuary, Kozhikode district, Kerala, India at 750m altitude.

Eragrostis nairii Kalidass C, J. Econ.Taxon. Bot. 39(1):126.2015(POACEAE).

Distribution: Simlipal Biosphere Reserve, Karanjia forest Division, Patbil, Mayurbhanj District of Odisha, India.

Eriocaulon biappendiculatum Manudev, Robi & Nampy, Edinburgh J. Bot. 72(2):219.2015 (ERIOCAULACEAE).

Distribution: Kurinjii Valley, Idukki District of Kerala, India at 1600m altitude.

Eriocaulon manoharanii Sunil & Naveen Kumar, Webbia 70(2): 211. 2015 (ERIOCAULACEAE).

Distribution: Pattimudi, Neryamangalam Forest Range, Ernakulam District of Kerala, India at 892m altitude.

Eriocaulon vandaanamense Sunil, Ratheesh et Sivadasan, Nordic J. Bot. 33(2):155.2015 (ERIOCAULACEAE).

Distribution: Vandaanam, Alappuzha District of Kerala, India.

Ficus anamalayana J.V. Sudhakar & G.V.S. Murthy, Rheedeia 25(1):1.2015(MORACEAE).

Distribution: Anamalai Tiger Reserve, in Coimbatore District of Tamil Nadu, India at 300m altitude.

Ficus jarawae G.K. Upadhyay & Chakrab., Phytodiversity 1(1 & 2):71. 2014 (MORACEAE).

Distribution: Dhani Nala, Jarawa Reserve Forest, Middle Andaman Island of Andaman & Nicobar islands, India.

Gentiana kurumbae Anilkumar & Udayan, Taiwania 60(2):81.2015(GENTIANACEAE).

Distribution: Attappady hills, Cherukolmala, Palakkad District of Kerala, India at 1750-1850m altitude.

Gentiana springateana D.Maity, Edinburgh J. Bot. 71(3):289.2014(GENTIANACEAE).

Distribution: Kalapathar and Muguthang, Sikkim, India at 4500-4800m altitude.

Gymnostachyum warrieranum K.M.P. Kumar, Balach.& V.B. Sreek., Kew Bulletin 70:40.2015 (ACANTHACEAE).

Distribution: Aralam Wildlife Sanctuary, Kannadivechakunnu, Kannur District of Kerala, India at 550m altitude.

Hedychium matthewii S. Thomas, B. Mani & S. J. Britto, Webbia 70(2): 221. 2015 (ZINGIBERACEAE).

Distribution: Idukki, the southern Western Ghats, Kerala, India, at 1200 m altitude.

Huberantha senjiana (R. Muralidharan, Naras. & N. Balach.), R. Muralidhaaran, Naras.& N. Balach., Phytotaxa 217(2):200.2015(ANNONACEAE).

Distribution: Pakkamalai Reserve Forest, Devathanampettai, Gingee, Villupuram District of Tamil Nadu, India at 250m altitude.

Impatiens adamowskiana Gogoi & Borah, Nordic J. Bot. 33: 586. 2015 (BALSAMINACEAE).

Distribution: 65 Point Mayodia, Lower Dibang Valley of Arunachal Pradesh, India, at 2600m altitude.

Impatiens ashihoi Gogoi & Borah, Phytotaxa 238 (3): 278.2015 (BALSAMINACEAE).

Distribution: Tiwari Gaon to Mayodia, Lower Dibang Valley of Arunachal Pradesh, India.

Impatiens courtallensis Ramas.&Pandur., Phytotaxa 203(2): 201. 2015 (BALSAMINACEAE).

Distribution: Courtallum hills (Agasthyamalai) way to Mylodai estate, Tirunelveli District of Tamil Nadu, India, at 788.24m altitude.

Impatiens dalaiensis Gogoi & Borah, Phytotaxa 207(3):286.2015(BALSAMINACEAE).

Distribution: Chaglagam on the way from Hyuliang, Anjaw District of Arunachal Pradesh, India, at 1517m altitude.

Impatiens neo-modesta Hareesh, K. M. P. Kumar & Sreekumar, Webbia 70(2):231.2015 (BALSAMINACEAE).

Distribution: Hill top, Nelliampathy forest, Palakkad District of Kerala, India, at 1400m altitude.

Impatiens pathakiana Gogoi & Borah, Telopea 18:121.2015 (BALSAMINACEAE).

Distribution: 20 km before Chaglagam, way from Hyuliang, Anjaw District of Arunachal Pradesh, India.

Impatiens sahyadrica V.B. Sreek.,Hareesh, Dantas & Sujanapal, Phytotaxa 207(3): 292. 2015 (BALSAMINACEAE).

Distribution: Sahyadri, Chembotti, Silent Valley, Palakkad district of Kerala, India, at 980m altitude.

Impatiens sasidharanii K.M.P.Kumar, Omalsree, Hareesh & V.B.Sreek., Phytotaxa 238(3):255.2015. (BALSAMINACEAE)

Distribution: Maattumala, Nelliampathy, Palakkad district of Kerala, India at 550m altitude.

Impatiens siangensis Gogoi, Phytotaxa 192(2):117.2015(BALSAMINACEAE).

Distribution: Locality between Pasighat and Along, East Siang District of Arunachal Pradesh, India.

Ischaemum kasaragodensis Dileep & G.G.Nair, Annals Pl. Sc. 4(10):1199.2015. (POACEAE)

Distribution: Badiyadukka, on the way to Mangalore, Kasaragod District of Kerala, India at 250m altitude.

Justicia sivadasanii Sunil, K.M.P. Kumar & Naveen Kum., Kew Bulletin 70:55. 2015 (ACANTHACEAE).

Distribution: Bhuthathankettu, Thundathil Forest Range, Ernakulam District of Kerala, India, at 50m altitude.

Kueferia pringlei D. Maity & Sentu K. Dey, Edinburgh J. Bot. 72(3):429.2015 (GENTIANACEAE).

Distribution: Kalapathar, near Muguthang Lake, North Sikkim district of Sikkim, India, at 4400m altitude.

Malaxis nilgiriensis T. Muthuk., A. Rajendran, Priyadh & Sarval., Webbia 70(1): 65. 2015 (ORCHIDACEAE).

Distribution: Mukurthi National Park, Nilgiri District, Tamil Nadu District, India.

Memecylon kurichiarensis Sivu, Aswathi. P & N. S. Pradeep, International Journal of Advanced Research 3(10): 1086. 2015 (MELASTOMATAACEAE).

Distribution: Kurichiarmala shola forest, Wayanad District, Western Ghats, Kerala, India, at 1436m altitude.

Oberonia manipurensis Chowlu, Nanda, A.N. Rao, Angela, Bishwajit & Akimpou, Nordic J. Bot.33:42.2015 (ORCHIDACEAE).

Distribution: Tamenglong, Tamenglong District of Manipur, India.

Oldenlandia dineshii Sojan & V. Suresh, Kew Bulletin 70:13.2015(RUBIACEAE).

Distribution: Nemmara, Palakkad District of Kerala, India, at 130m altitude.

Ophiorhiza sahyadriensis Hareesh, V.B. Sreek.& K.M.P. Kumar, Phytotaxa 202(3): 219. 2015. (RUBIACEAE).

Distribution: Walakkad, Silent Valey, Palakkad District of Kerala, India at 1100m altitude.

Pennilabium labanyaeanum C. Deori, N.Odyuo & A.A. Mao, Gard. Bull. Singapore 67(1):143.2015 (ORCHIDACEAE).

Distribution: Laitkyrhong, 5km from Smith, East Khasi Hills District of Meghalaya, India at 1753m altitude.

Rhododendron mechukae A.A.Mao & A.Paul, Edinburgh J. Bot. 70(1): 57. 2013 (ERICACEAE).

Distribution: Mechuka to Yourlung, West Siang District of Arunachal Pradesh, India at an altitude

of 2436m altitude.

Rhododendron pseudomaddenii A.A.Mao & M. Bhaumik, Edinburgh J. Bot. 72(2): 209.2015 (ERICACEAE).

Distribution: Yourlung to Lamang, West Siang District of Arunachal Pradesh, India at 3000m altitude.

Rhododendron titapuriense A.A. Mao, K.N.E. Cox & D.F. Chamb, Plantsman 26.2013(ERICACEAE).

Distribution: Near Hanuman Camp, Yang Sang valley, Anjaw District of Arunachal Pradesh, India at 2350m altitude.

Salacia wayanadica Sujana, Nagaraju, Ratheesh & Anil Kumar, Taiwania 60(2):91.2015 (CELASTRACEAE).

Distribution: Chandanathode, Periya, Wayanad District of Kerala, India at 853m altitude.

Scurrula paramjitii L.J. Singh, Taiwania 60(3):123.2015 (LORANTHACEAE).

Distribution: APWD Guest House, Ranghat, Middle Andaman District of Andaman & Nicobar Islands, India at 105m altitude.

Sonerila gadgiliana Ratheesh & Sivadasan, Bangladesh J. Plant Taxon. 22(1):9.2015 (MELASTOMATACEAE).

Distribution: Banasuramala, Wayanad District of Kerala, India at 1700m altitude.

Sonerila keralensis Deepthikum.&Pandur., TAPROBANICA6 (2):72.2014. (MELASTOMATACEAE)

Distribution: Thirunelli, Wayanad District of Kerala, India at 1000m altitude.

Sonerila vythiriensis Ratheesh, Nandakumar & Sujana, Annals Plant Sc. 3(11):863. 2014 (MELASTOMATACEAE).

Distribution: Vythiri hills, Wayanad District of Kerala, India at 110m altitude.

Stellaria devendrae Pusalkar & S.K. Srivast., Nordic J. Bot. 33(4): 385. 2015 (CARYOPHYLLACEAE).

Distribution: Phata-Trijuginarayan, Rudraprayag District, Garhwal Division of Uttarakhand, India at 2000m altitude.

Striga kamalii Omalsree, K.M. prabhu, M.Sabu & Sunojkumar, Phytotaxa 212(2):163.2015 (OROBANCHACEAE).

Distribution: Bharathiar University Campus, Coimbatore District of Tamil Nadu, India at 450m altitude.

Swertia raveendrae Shahina & Nampy, Phytotaxa 195(1): 44.2015(GENTIANACEAE).

Distribution: Babudan hills, Chickmagalur District of Karnataka, India at 1895m altitude.

Thamnocalamus arunachalensis Naithani, Indian For. 141(5):588.2015(POACEAE).

Distribution: Segong, Machuka, West Siang District of Arunachal Pradesh, India at 1800m altitude.

Tripogon idukkianus Sunil & Pradeep., Phytotaxa 202 (4):294.2015 (POACEAE).

Distribution: Ramakkalmedu, Idukki District of Kerala, India, at 1500m altitude.

Tripogon mahendragiriensis Chorghe, Sangita Dey, K.Prasad, Prasanna & Y.V.Rao, Nordic J. Bot. 33(6):655.2015 (POACEAE).

Distribution: Mahendragiri Hills, Gajapati District of Odisha, India at 1478m altitude.

Vernonia kannikattiensis T.J.S. Rajakumar, R. Selvakumari, S. Murugesan & N. Chellaperumal, Indian J. Forestry 38(3):269.2015(ASTERACEAE).

Distribution: Kallivarpulmottai near Kannikatti, Kallivarpulmottai Watch Tower and Motbukuzhivayal near Kothaiyar, Tirunelveli District of Tamil Nadu, India at 1000-1200m altitude.

Vigna pandeyana R.D. Gore, S.P. Gaikwad & S.D. Randive, Biodiversity Data Journal 3:e4606.2015. (FABACEAE)

Distribution: Chalkewadi, Sahyadri range, Satara District of Maharashtra, India at 1050m altitude.

Zingiber bipinianum D.K.Roy, D. Verma, A.D. Talukdar & M.Dutta Choudhury, J. Jpn. Bot. 90.298.2015 (ZINGIBERACEAE).

Distribution: Teptepa, Balpakram National Park, Hatisia Beat, South Garo Hills District of Meghalaya, India at 257m altitude.

Zingiber mizoramensis Ram.Sushil K. Singh &

S. Sharma, Phytotaxa 233(1): 080. 2015 (ZINGIBERACEAE).

Distribution: Murlen National Park, Champhai District of Mizoram, India.

Zingiber murlenica Ram. Kumar, Sushil K. Singh & S. Sharma, Phytotaxa 233(1): 080. 2015 (ZINGIBERACEAE).

Distribution: Murlen National Park, Champhai District of Mizoram, India.

NEW VARIETY

Impatiens sasiharanii var. **hirsuta** K.M.P. Kumar, Omalsree, Hareesh & V.B.Sreek., Phytotaxa 238(3):255.2015(BALSAMINACEAE).

Distribution: Minnampara, Nelliampathy, Palakkad District of Kerala, India, at 550m altitude.

Molineria prainiana Deb var. **josephii** D.K.Roy, D.Verma & A.D. Talukdar, J. Jap. Bot. 90(1):61.2015 (HYPOXIDACEAE).

Distribution: Namdapha, Changlang District of Arunachal Pradesh, India, at 475m altitude.

Rhizophora mucronata var. **alokii** P. Ragavan, Phytokeys 52:95.2015(RHIZOPHORACEAE).

Distribution: Austin Creek, mangrove forest, North Andaman, India.

Scleria neesii Kunth var. **gadchiroliensis** Govekar, Sardesai & Kahalkar, Taiwania 60(4):181. 2015(CYPERACEAE).

Distribution: Kotagudam, Aheri, Gadchiroli district of Maharashtra, India, at 150m altitude.

NEW SUB-SPECIES

Adenophora capillaris Hemsleysubsp. **dzukoensis** A.A. Mao, Nandita Sharma & D.K. Roy, Pleione 9(1):211.2015(CAMPANULACEAE).

Distribution: Dzukou valley, Nagaland, India, at 2400-2700m altitude.

Cassiope fastigiata (Wall.) D. Don subsp. **sennikovii** D. Maity, Feddes Repert. 125:72.2014 (ERICACEAE).

Distribution: Kalapathar and Muguthang, Sikkim, India, at 4300-4800m altitude.

NEW DISTRIBUTIONAL RECORDS

Genus

Bromelia L. (BROMELIACEAE)

Distribution: Vikramshila Gangetic Dolphin Wildlife Sanctuary, Kahalgaon, Bhagalpur, Bihar, India at 39-48m altitude.

Species

Aeschynanthus angustiblondus W.T. Wang (GESNERIACEAE)

Distribution: Tirap, Changlang of Arunachal Pradesh and Kohima, Nagaland.

Artabotrys suaveolens (Blume) Blume (ANNONACEAE)

Distribution: East-West Road, Great Nicobar Biosphere Reserve and Afra Bay, Andaman & Nicobar Islands, at 20-131m.

Bromelia penguin L. (BROMELIACEAE)

Distribution: Vikramshila Gangetic Dolphin Wildlife Sanctuary, Kahalgaon, Bhagalpur, Bihar, India at 39-48m altitude.

Carpesium cordatum F.H. Chen & C.M. Hu (ASTERACEAE)

Distribution: Kukinakh, Gangi, Uttarkashi District of Garhwal Himalaya, Uttarakhand, India, at 2800-3000m altitude.

Eleocaris attenuata (Franch. & Sav.) Palla (CYPERACEAE)

Distribution: Western Ghats, Thirunelli, Wayanad District of Kerala, India, at 847m altitude.

Eria merguensis Lindl. (ORCHIDACEAE)

Distribution: Murlen National Park, Champhai District of Mizoram, India at 1550m altitude.

Heterotis rotundifolia (Sm.) Jacq.-Fel. (MELASTOMATACEAE)

Distribution: Rangat, Kalsi and Diglipur of Andaman & Nicobar Islands.

Hyoscyamus albus L. (SOLANACEAE)

Distribution: YSR Horticultural University Herbal Garden, Rajendra Nagar, Telangana, at 555m altitude.

Impatiens fugongensis K.M. Liu & Y.Y. Cong (BALSAMINACEAE)

Distribution: Myodia, 2-3km ahead towards Hunli, Dibang Valley District, Arunachal Pradesh, at

2100m altitude.

Impatiens yui S.H. Huang (BALSAMINACEAE)

Distribution: Myodia, near Shiv Mandir, Arunachal Pradesh.

Impatiens xanthiana H.F. Comber (BALSAMINACEAE)

Distribution: Chaglagam, Anjaw District of Arunachal Pradesh.

Ixora longibracteata Bremek. (RUBIACEAE)

Distribution: Kodalbasthi Range, Jaldapara National Park, Chilapata Range, Nalrajabadi and Baniya, Jalpaiguri District, West Bengal.

Kobresia loliacea F.T. Wang & Tang ex P.C. Li (CYPERACEAE)

Distribution: Kanebang to Pao Camp, Upper Siang District, Arunachal Pradesh, at 3000m altitude.

Memecylon capitellatum L. (MEMECYLACEAE)

Distribution: Way to Periaaravi Valley, Alagar Hills, Dindigul District of Tamil Nadu, at 460m altitude.

Rubus sengorensis Grierson & D.G. Long (ROSACEAE)

Distribution: Dibang Valley, Arunachal Pradesh.

Saurauia sinohirsuta J.Q. Li & Soejarto (ACTINIDIACEAE)

Distribution: Gima gida river bank near Garu, West Siang District, at 900m and Boleng to Along road, East Siang district of Arunachal Pradesh.

VARIETAL RECORDS

Acmella radicans var. **debilis** (H.B.K.) Jansen (ASTERACEAE)

Distribution: Amba, Kolhapur District, Maharashtra and Chorla Ghat, Belghum District of Karnataka.

Cirsium arvense L. var. **alpestre** Nageli (ASTERACEAE)

Distribution: Western Himalaya, Garhwal and Kumaun of Uttarakhand.

Galium boreale L. var. **ciliatum** Nakai (RUBIACEAE)

Distribution: Dhopardhar, Tehri, Uttarakhand,

India, at 1400m altitude.

Galium boreale L. var. **intermedium** DC. (RUBIACEAE)

Distribution: Dras, Ladakh, Jammu & Kashmir, India, at 2700m altitude.

Ophiorrhiza rugosa Wall. var. **angustifolia** Ridsdale (RUBIACEAE)

Distribution: Walakkad, Silent National Park, Palakkad District and Sugandhagiri of Wayanad District of Kerala.

Paris polyphylla Smith var. **nana** H. Li (LILIACEAE)

Distribution: Rishop, Darjeeling District of West Bengal.

SUBSPECIES RECORDS

Commelina africana L. subsp. **zanzibarica** Faden (COMMELINACEAE)

Distribution: Calicut University Campus, near Villoonniyal Temple, Malappuram District of Kerala.

Cyperus conglomeratus subsp. **curvulus** (Boeckeler) Kukkonen (CYPERACEAE).

Distribution: Balab garden farm, Bikaner District of Rajasthan.

PTERIDOPHYTES

New Genus

Katoella Fraser-Jenk. Ferns and Fern-allies of Nepal 1.33.2015 (DAVALLIACEAE).

Distribution: India

New Species

Arthromeris himalovata Fraser-Jenk. & Kandel, Ferns and Fern-allies of Nepal 1.34.2015 (POLYPODIACEAE).

Distribution: Singalilla ridge, Pashupatinagar near the Nepalese border with India.

Dryopteris kashmiriana Fraser-Jenk. & Widén. Ferns and Fern-allies of Nepal 1.26.2015 (DRYOPTERIDACEAE).

Distribution: Gund hamlet, Sonamarg – Ganderbal in the Sind valley, of Jammu & Kashmir, India at 2400m.

Dryopteris subcochleata Fraser-Jenk. & K.C. Rajkumar, Ferns and Fern-allies of Nepal 1.27.2015 (DRYOPTERIDACEAE).

Distribution: N.W. side of bottom of gorge of Wah -Umkhrah river, below Beadon Fall, near Mawlai, N.W. side of Shillong town, Khasi Hills district of Meghalaya, India.

Huperzia cavei Fraser-Jenk. & B.S.Kholia, Ferns and Fern-allies of Nepal 1.46.2015 (LYCOPODIACEAE).

Distribution: Eumtso La (Pass) Sikkim, India.

Onychium kholianum Fraser-Jenk. & S.Matsumoto, Ferns and Fern-allies of Nepal 1.292.2015 (DRYOPTERIDACEAE).

Distribution: Gini, Thal on road up to ridge south of Munsiyari, Pithoragarh district of Uttarakhand, India.

Onychium vermae Fraser-Jenk. & Khullar, Ferns and Fern-allies of Nepal 1.300.2015 (DRYOPTERIDACEAE).

Distribution: Lebong race course, Darjeeling district of West Bengal, India, at 1600m.

Polypodiodes simonsiana Fraser-Jenk. & Shalimov, Turczaninowia 18 (3): 114. 2015 (POLYPODIACEAE).

Distribution: North Triangle (Arahku) Kachin state, Myanmar and distributed in North East India (Arunachal Pradesh, Manipur & Meghalaya).

Pteris dixitii Fraser-Jenk. & Pariyar, Ferns and Fern-allies of Nepal 1.329.2015 (PTERIDACEAE).

Distribution: Shillong peak, Meghalaya, India.

Selaginella emodi Fraser-Jenk., Ferns and Fern-allies of Nepal 1.67.2015 (SELAGINELLACEAE).

Distribution: Dhunche to Chandanbari and Gossainkund, Rasuwa District, Central Nepal and distributed in Arunachal Pradesh, Sikkim, Darjeeling, Uttarakhand and South India.

Tectaria pseudosiifolia Fraser-Jenk. & Wangdi, Ferns and Fern-allies of Nepal 1.31.2015 (DRYOPTERIDACEAE).

Distribution: Samdrup Jongkhar district, Bhutan and also distributed above Seinki Park, Itanagar of Arunachal Pradesh, India.

NEW SUB-SPECIES

Dryopteris wallichiana subsp. **bhutanica** Fraser-Jenk. & Pariyar, Ferns and Fern-allies of Nepal

1.28.2015 (DRYOPTERIDACEAE).

Distribution: Arunachal Pradesh, India.

NEW DISTRIBUTIONAL RECORDS

Tectaria puberula (Desv.) C. Chr (DRYOPTERIDACEAE).

Distribution: Moozhayah forest of Pathanamthitta district of Kerala, India, at 1010m.

Bryophytes

NEW SPECIES

Plagiochila arunachalensis Shuvadeep Majumdar and D.K. Singh, NeBio 6 (4): 8. 2015. (PLAGIOCHILACEAE)

Distribution: Anjaw district of Arunachal Pradesh, India at 3400m.

NEW DISTRIBUTIONAL RECORDS

Neolepidozia wallichiana (Gottsche) Fulford & J. Taylor (LEPIDOZIACEAE).

Distribution: Anjaw and Lower Dibang Valley districts of Arunachal Pradesh at 1650 and 950m altitude.

Bazzania angustistipula N. Kitag. (LEPIDOZIACEAE)

Distribution: Anjaw and West Siang districts of Arunachal Pradesh and West district of Sikkim at 2875 and 2982m altitude.

Bazzania hainanensis L.-P. Zhou & L. Zhang (LEPIDOZIACEAE)

Distribution: Champhai-Khawzawl of Mizoram at 1320m altitude.

Ceratolejeunea belangeriana (Gottsche) Steph. (LEJEUNEACEAE)

Distribution: Coimbatore District of Tamil Nadu at 1040m altitude.

Cololejeunea microscopica (Taylor) Schiffn. var. **exigua** (A. Evans) Pócs (LEJEUNEACEAE)

Distribution: Palni hills of Tamil Nadu at 2310m altitude.

Plagiochila biondiana C. Massal. (PLAGIOCHILACEAE)

Distribution: North District of Sikkim at 3419 and 3590m altitude.

Plagiochila ptychanthoidea Steph.
(PLAGIOCHILACEAE)

Distribution: Dampa, Bambu and Ngengpui Wildlife Sanctuary of Mizoram at 291 and 138m altitude.

Radula retroflexa Taylor (RADULACEAE)

Distribution: Anjaw district of Arunachal Pradesh and North district of Sikkim at 820 and 923m altitude.

Riccardia tamariscina(Steph.)Schiffn.
(ANEURACEAE)

Distribution:South Andaman and Little Nicobar of Andaman & Nicobar Islands at 19 and 33m altitude.

Solenostoma baueri (Schiffn.) Steph.
(SOLENOTOMATACEAE)

Distribution:East and West districts of Sikkim at 2000 and 2150m altitude.

Solenostoma fusiforme (Steph.) R.M. Schust.
(SOLENOTOMATACEAE)

Distribution: East district of Sikkim at 3109m altitude.

Solenostoma vulcanicola(Schiffn.) Vaða,
Hentschel & Heinrichs

(SOLENOTOMATACEAE)

Distribution:East district of Sikkim at 1600m altitude.

Syrrhodon parasiticus (Brid.)Besch.
(CALYMPERACEAE)

Distribution: Wayanad district of Kerala at 800m altitude.

Thysananthus fruticosus (Lindenb.& Gottsche)
Schiffn. (LEJEUNEACEAE)

Distribution: Great Nicobar Island of Andaman & Nicobar Islands at 47–73m altitude.

Thysananthus comosus Lindenb.ex Lehm.
(LEJEUNEACEAE)

Distribution: Andaman & Nicobar Islands.

VARIETAL RECORDS

Thysananthus convolutus Lindenb.var.
convolutus (LEJEUNEACEAE)

Distribution: Andaman & Nicobar Islands.

Thysananthus gottschei (J.B. Jack & Steph.)Steph.var. **gottschei** (LEJEUNEACEAE)

Distribution: Andaman & Nicobar Islands.

SUBSPECIES RECORDS

Thysananthus retusus (Reinw., Blume & Nees)
B.Thiers & Gradst. subsp. **retusus**
(LEJEUNEACEAE)

Distribution: Andaman & Nicobar Islands.

Lichens

NEW SPECIES

Acanthothecis subconsociansPooja Gupta & G.P. Sinha, J. New Biological Reports 4(2): 103. 2015
(GRAPHIDACEAE).

Distribution: Pangthang–Rokshe, East Sikkim District, Sikkim, India.

Coenogonium dattatreyaense Shraavan Kumar S. & Y.L. Krishnamurthy, Kavaka 44: 64. 2015
(COENOGONIACEAE).

Distribution: Chandra-Drona hill, Chikkamagaluru, Karnataka, India.

Coenogonium kiggaense Shraavan Kumar S & Y.L. Krishnamurthy, Kavaka 44: 63. 2015
(COENOGONIACEAE).

Distribution: Kigga evergreen forest, Chikkamagaluru, Karnataka, India.

Gyalidea corticolaPooja Gupta & G.P. Sinha,
Current Research in Environmental & Applied
Mycology 5(2): 145. 2015(SOLORINELLACEAE).

Distribution: Penangla, Sikkim, India

Melaspilea amarkantakensis S. Joseph & G. P. Sinha, Taiwania 60(1):18. 2015(MELASPILEACEAE).

Distribution: Ma Ki Bagiya, Amarkantak, Anuppur district, Madhya Pradesh, India

Stigmatochroma microspora Mohabe, Nayaka & A.M. Reddy, J. New Biological Reports (JNBR) 4(2): 128. 2015(PHYCIACEAE).

Distribution: Nalakaluva village, Kurnool district, Andhra Pradesh, India.

Synarthonia psoromica S. Joseph & G. P. Sinha,
Lichenologist 47(2):128.2015(AETHONIACEAE).

Distribution: Arnbi Forest, Nilgiris, Tamil Nadu, India

Synarthonia sikkimensis S. Joseph & G. P. Sinha, Lichenologist 47(2): 128. 2015 (AETHONIACEAE).

Distribution: Yakche, Lachung-Dombang, Sikkim, India.

NEW DISTRIBUTIONAL RECORDS

Agonimia opuntiella (Buschardt & Poelt) Vzda (VERRUCARIACEAE)

Distribution: Mount Abu, Sirohi district, Rajasthan.

Arthopyrenia saxicola A. Massal. (ARTHOPYRENIACEAE)

Distribution: Mehao Wildlife Sanctuary, Lower Debang Valley district, Arunachal Pradesh.

Arthothelium subbessale (Nyl.) Makhija & Patw. (ARTHONIACEAE)

Distribution: Subansiri River bed, Taliha, Upper Subansiri district, Arunachal Pradesh.

Aulaxina dictyospora R. Sant. (GOMPHILLACEAE)

Distribution: Andaman Islands, Middle Andaman.

Aulaxina opegraphina Fée (GOMPHILLACEAE)

Distribution: Little Andaman Island of Andaman Islands.

Bulbothrix ventricosa (Hale & Kurokawa) Hale (PARMELIACEAE)

Distribution: Andaman Islands.

Byssoloma ezdanum Sérus. (GOMPHILLACEAE)

Distribution: Andaman Islands.

Calenia graphidea Vain. (GOMPHILLACEAE)

Distribution: Andaman Islands.

Chaenothecopsis savanica (Räsänen) Tibell (MYCOCALICIACEAE)

Distribution: Van Vibhag parishad fores, Kachahari Road, Polibhit district, Uttar Pradesh.

Chiodecton malmei G. Thor (ROCELLACEAE)

Distribution: Andaman Islands.

Cryptothecia irregularis Lücking, Aptroot, Kalb & Elix (ARTHONIACEAE)

Distribution: Andaman Islands.

Diorygma macgregorii (Vain.) Kalb, Staiger & Elix (GRAPHIDACEAE)

Distribution: Bhaulkpong-Tenga, West Kameng district, Arunachal Pradesh.

Diorygma pachygraphum (Nyl.) Kalb, Staiger & Elix (GRAPHIDACEAE)

Distribution: Mehao Wildlife Sanctuary, Lower Debang Valley district, Arunachal Pradesh.

Graphis crassilabra Müll. Arg. (GRAPHIDACEAE)

Distribution: Balpakgram forest, West Garo hills district, Meghalaya.

Graphis nuda (Magn.) Staiger & Lücking (GRAPHIDACEAE)

Distribution: Mehao Wildlife Sanctuary, Lower Debang Valley district, Arunachal Pradesh.

Graphis oligospora Zahlbr. *apud* Handel-Mazzetti (GRAPHIDACEAE)

Distribution: Mehao Wildlife Sanctuary, Lower Debang Valley district, Arunachal Pradesh.

Graphis paraserpens Lizano & Lücking (GRAPHIDACEAE)

Distribution: Sessa, West Kameng district, Arunachal Pradesh.

Graphis pavoniana Fée. (GRAPHIDACEAE)

Distribution: Mokokchung-Mekong forest, Mokokchung district, Nagaland.

Graphis renschiana (Müll. Arg.) Stizenb. (GRAPHIDACEAE)

Distribution: Tipi, West Kameng district, Arunachal Pradesh.

Herpothallon japonicum (Zahlbr.) G. Thor (ARTHONIACEAE)

Distribution: Phakui Wildlife Sanctuary, East Kameng district, Arunachal Pradesh.

Julellavitrispora (Cooke & Harkness) M.E. Barr (ARTHOPYRENIACEAE)

Distribution: Mount Abu, Sirohi district, Rajasthan.

Malmideapsychotrioides (Kalb & Lücking) Kalb, Rivas Plata & Lumbsch (MALMIDEACEAE)

Distribution: Mount Abu, Sirohi district, Rajasthan.

Megalospora atrorubricans (Nyl.) Zahlbr. (MEGALOSPORACEAE)

Distribution: Shergoan, West Kameng district, Arunachal Pradesh.

Mycoblastus affinis (Schaer) Schauer (MYCOBLASTACEAE)

Distribution: Hotspring-Jachup, Anjaw district, Arunachal Pradesh.

Opegrapha subdimidiata Ertz (ROCCEL-LACEAE)

Distribution: Bitta, 24-Parganas district, West Bengl.

Opegrapha xerica Torrente & Egea (ROCCEL-LACEAE)

Distribution: Yakche, Lachung, Sikkim.

Opegrapha pheophyciae R. Sant. (ROCCEL-LACEAE)

Distribution: Thal Ke Dhar, Pithoragarh, Uttarakhand.

Porina tijucana Vain. (PORINACEAE)

Distribution: Shergoan, West Kameng district, Arunachal Pradesh.

Porina sphaerocephala Vain. (PORINACEAE)

Distribution: Andaman Islands.

Protoparmelia hesperia (Kantvilas & Elix) Kantvilas, Papong & Lumbsch (PARMELIACEAE)

Distribution: Panbarie Tea-Garden, Panbarie, Dhubri district, Assam.

Relicina relicinula (Müll. Arg.) Hale (PARMELIACEAE)

Distribution: Katchal Island of the Nicobar Islands.

Rhabdodiscus crassus (Müll. Arg.) Rivas (GRAPHIDACEAE)

Distribution: Mehao Wildlife Sanctuary, Lower Debang Valley district, Arunachal Pradesh.

Staurothele rugulosa (A. Massal.) Arnold (VERRUCARIACEAE)

Distribution: Sajjangarh Wildlife Sanctuary, Rajasthan.

Strigula microspora Lücking (STRIGULACEAE)

Distribution: Andaman Islands.

Stirtonia punctiformis Aptroot & Sipman (ARTHONIACEAE)

Distribution: Kalain Tea-Garden, Kalain, Cachar district, Assam.

Trichothelium bipindense F. Schill. (PORINACEAE)

Distribution: Andaman Islands.

Willeya diffractella (Nyl.) Müll. Arg. (VERRUCARIACEAE)

Distribution: Kusalidra forest, Sawaimadhopur, Rajasthan.

Fungi

NEW SPECIES

Acroconidiella indicata B. Prasher and R. K. Verma, Journal on New Biological Reports 4(2): 111.2015 (DAVIDIELLACEAE)

Distribution: Solan district of Himachal Pradesh, India.

Acroconidiella manoharacharii B. Prasher and R. K. Verma, Journal on New Biological Reports 4(2): 113.2015 (DAVIDIELLACEAE)

Distribution: Tara Devi, Shimla district of Himachal Pradesh, India.

Agaricus flavistipus Atri, M. Kaur and A. Kaur, Kavaka 42:22.2014 (AGRICACEAE).

Distribution: Swaag, Faridkot of Punjab at 196m.

Agaricus stellatus-cuticus Atri, M. Kaur and A. Kaur, Kavaka 42:20.2014 (AGRICACEAE).

Distribution: Qila Rehmatgarh, Sangrur of Punjab at 231m.

Antrodiella indica G. Kaur, Avneet P. Singh & Dhingra, Mycotaxon 130.625.2015 (PHANEROCHAETACEAE).

Distribution: Sector 18-D Park, Chandigarh, Punjab, India.

Amanita altusdenticulata Yadwinder Singh & Munruchi Kaur, Journal on New Biological Reports 4(1):51.2015 (AMANITACEAE).

Distribution: Summer Hills, Shimla district of Himachal Pradesh, India at 2000m.

Amanita kedarnathensis Yadwinder Singh & Munruchi Kaur, JOURNAL ON NEW BIOLOGICAL

REPORTS 4(1):53.2015. (*AMANTACEAE*)

Distribution: Kund area, Kedarnath of Rudraprayag district of Uttarakhand, India at 1800m.

Austroboletus olivaceoglutinosus K. Das & Dentinger, Kew Bulletin 15.70.2015.

(BOLETACEAE)

Distribution: Lachen top, North district of Sikkim, India at 2846m.

Boletus lakhanpalii K. Das, D. Chakr., A. Baghela, S.K. Singh & Dentinger, Sydowia 67:15.2015 (*BOLETACEAE*).

Distribution: Dombang, North district of Sikkim, India at 2920m.

Boletus recapitulatus D. Chakr., K. Das, A. Baghela, S.K. Singh & Dentinger, Phytotaxa 234 (2):152.2015 (*Boletaceae*).

Distribution: Churten, East district of Sikkim, India at 1454m.

Bondarzewia zonata K. Das, A. Parihar & Hembrom, Turk. J. Bot. 39:129.2015. (*BONDARZEWIACEAE*)

Distribution: Dombang, North district of Sikkim, India at 2829m.

Camposporium himalayanum I. B. Prasher & R. K. Verma, Cryptogamie Mycologie, 36 (2):130.2015 (*Botryosphaerales*).

Distribution: Sundernagar, Himachal Pradesh, India at 2829m.

Cantharellus sikkimensis K. Das, Buyck, D. Chakr., A. Baghela, S.K. Singh & V. Hofstetter, Phytotaxa 222 (4):273.2015 (*CANTHARELLACEAE*).

Distribution: Shingba Rhododendron Wildlife Sanctuary, North district of Sikkim, India at 3208m.

Chlorolepiota brunneotincta N. S. Atri, B.Kumari & R. C. Upadhyay, Turk. J. Bot.38: 370.2015 (*AGARICACEAE*).

Distribution: Kather, Solan district of Himachal Pradesh, India at 1650m.

Clitocybula sulcata K.N.A. Raj & Manim. Phytotaxa 208 (1):65.2015 (*MARASMIACEAE*).

Distribution: Atholi, Kozhikode district of Kerala, India.

Corneriella indica Raj & Manim. Phytotaxa 213 (2): 107.2015. (*TRICHOLOMATACEAE*)

Distribution: Peechi forest, Thrissur district of Kerala, India.

Datronia ustulatiligna Har.Kaur, G. Kaur & Dhingra, Mycotaxon 130.295.2015 (*POLYPOURACEAE*).

Distribution: Rampur, Shimla district of Himachal Pradesh, India.

Dictyosporium hydeii B. Prasher & R.K. Verma, Phytotaxa 204 (3): 196.2015 (*DICTYOSPHAERIACEAE*).

Distribution: Bilaspur of Himachal Pradesh, India.

Dictyosporium indicum I. B. Prasher & R. K. Verma, Phytotaxa 204(3):194.2015 (*DICTYOSPHAERIACEAE*).

Distribution: Mandi district of Himachal Pradesh, India.

Galerina indica K. P. D. Latha & Manim., Mycoscience 56:76.2015. (*HYMENOGASTRACEAE*).

Distribution: Muthanga Wildlife Sanctuary, Wayanad district of Kerala, India.

Hyphoderma hallenbergii Man. Kaur, Avneet P. Singh & Dhingra, Mycotaxon 130.223.2015 (*MERULIACEAE*).

Distribution: Baghi road, Narkanda, Shimla district of Himachal Pradesh, India.

Hyphodontia dhingrae Samita & Sanyal, Mycotaxon 129(1).209.2015 (*SCHIZOPORACEAE*).

Distribution: Kausani, Bageshwar district of Uttarakhand, India.

Lactarius indo-chryso-rheus K. Das & Verbeken, Mycotaxon 130.110.2015 (*RUSSULACEAE*).

Distribution: Dombang, North district of Sikkim, India at 2920.

Lactarius olivaceoglutinosus K. Das & Verbeken, Mycotaxon 130.110.2015 (*RUSSULACEAE*).

Distribution: Shingba Rhododendron sanctuary, North district of Sikkim, India at 3252m.

Lactarius pyriodorus K. Das & Verbeken, Mycotaxon 130.118.2015 (*RUSSULACEAE*).

Distribution: Dombang, North district of Sikkim, India at 2975m.

Lactarius yumthangensis K. Das & Verbeke, Mycotaxon 130.124.2015 (RUSSULACEAE).

Distribution: Yumthang valley of Shingba Rhododendron Sanctuary, North district of Sikkim, India at 3586m.

Lepiota indica B. Kumari & N.S. Atri, Turk. J. Bot. 37: 1188.2013 (AGARICACEAE).

Distribution: Korba, Chakrata Road, Uttarakhand, India.

Lepiota attenuispora B. Kumari & N.S. Atri, Turk. J. Bot. 37: 1191.2013 (AGARICACEAE).

Distribution: campus of Botany department, Punjabi University, Patiala, Punjab, India.

Leptocorticium indicum Samita, Sanyal & Dhingra, Mycotaxon 129(2).361.2014 (CORTICIACEAE).

Distribution: Kaddukhal, Tehri Garhwal district of Uttarakhand, India.

Limacella magna B. Kumari & R.C. Upadhyay, Turk. J. Bot. 37: 1191.2013 (Amanitaceae).

Distribution: Solan district of Himachal Pradesh, India 1650m.

Lysurus habungianus G. Gogoi & V. Parkash, Curr. Res. Environ. Appl. Mycol., 5 (3): 248.2015 (PHALLACEAE).

Distribution: Habungia village, Jorhat district of Assam, India, at 102m.

Marasmius indopurpureostriatus K. Das, A.K. Dutta & K. Acharya, Mycosphere 6 (5): 563.2015 (MARASMIACEAE).

Distribution: Churten, East district of Sikkim, India 1454m.

Metacordyceps dhauladharensis Sapan, Turk. J. Bot. 39: 521.2015 (CLAVICIPITACEAE).

Distribution: Dhauladhar mountain range, Himachal Pradesh India 2200m.

Muscodor ghoomensis Meshram, Mahiti G., Saxena S., Sydowia 67:136.2015

(XYLARIACEAE).

Distribution: Ghoom monastery of Darjeeling district of West Bengal, India.

Muscodor indica Meshram, Mahiti G., Saxena

S., Sydowia 67:136.2015 (XYLARIACEAE).

Distribution: Ghoom monastery of Darjeeling district of West Bengal, India.

Muscodor tigerii S. Saxena, Meshram & N. Kapoor, Ann. Microbiol. 65:53.2015 (XYLARIACEAE).

Distribution: Tiger Hill area of Darjeeling district of West Bengal, India.

Neosporidesmium appendiculatus Prasher I. B. and Verma R. K., Mycol. Progress 14:87.1. 2015 (DISTOSEPTISPORACEAE).

Distribution: Panjab University Campus, Chandigarh, Punjab, India at 355m.

Neosporidesmium macrosporum Prasher I. B. and Verma R. K., Nova Hedwigia 100 (1-2): 269.2015 (DISTOSEPTISPORACEAE).

Distribution: Panjab University Campus, Chandigarh, Punjab, India at 355m.

Panaeolus cyanoannulatus Atri, M. Kaur & A. Kaur, J. New Biol. Reports 3(2): 126.2014. (PSATHYRELLACEAE)

Distribution: Jeewanpur Jattan, Hoshiarpur district of Punjab, India at 295m altitude.

Panaeolus lepus-stercus Atri, M. Kaur & A. Kaur, J. New Biol. Reports 3(2): 129.2014 (PSATHYRELLACEAE).

Distribution: Sheep and Rabbit Breeding Farm, Dalla Dhar, Pathankot district of Punjab, India at 309m altitude.

Phlebiopsis punjabensis G. Kaur, Avneet P. Singh & Dhingra, Mycotaxon 130.907.2015 (PHANEROCHAETACEAE).

Distribution: Ropar boat club, Ropar, Punjab, India.

Prillieuxina aeglicola A. K. Gautam, Curr. Res. Environ. Appl. Mycol., 5 (1): 71. 2015 (ASTERINACEAE).

Distribution: Berthin, Bilaspur district of Himachal Pradesh, India 686m.

Rickenella indica K. P. D. Latha & Manim., Mycoscience 56:78.2015 (REPETOBASIDIACEAE).

Distribution: Muthanga Wildlife Sanctuary, Wayanad district of Kerala, India.

Russula kanadii A.K. Dutta & K. Acharya, Turk. J. Bot. 39:4.2015 (RUSSULACEAE).

Distribution: Gurguripal forest, West Midnapur district of West Bengal, India at 56m.

Schiffnerula dioscoriae Lini K. Mathew, Neeta N. Nair & S. Swapna, Curr. Res. Environ. Appl. Mycol., 5 (1): 18. 2015 (ENGLERULACEAE).

Distribution: Urakuzhy water falls, Malabar Wildlife Sanctuary of Kerala, India 686m.

Scytalidium aeglicola Gautam A K, Curr. Res. Environ. Appl. Mycol. 4 (1): 8. 2015 (DEMATIACEAE).

Distribution: Bilaspur district of Himachal Pradesh, India 2208m.

Sporidesmium biligiriense Dubey and Sengupta., Curr. Res. Environ. Appl. Mycol. 5 (4): 391.2015.

Distribution: Biligiri Rangaswamy Temple Wildlife Sanctuary of Karnataka, India.

Suillus adiharii K. Das, D. Chakr. & Cotter, Phytotaxa 219 (3): 290.2015 (SUILLACEAE).

Distribution: Dombang, North district of Sikkim, India at 2890m.

Suillus lariciphilus K. Das, D. Chakr., K.P.D. Latha & Cotter, Cryptogamie Mycologie 36(2): 155.2015 (SUILLACEAE).

Distribution: Dombang, North district of Sikkim, India at 2890m.

Tubulicrinis indicus Jyoti Sharma, Avneet P. Singh & Dhingra, Mycotaxon 130.879.2015 (TUBULICRINACEAE).

Distribution: Duggi, Bhadarwah, Doda district of Jammu & Kashmir, India.

NEW VARIETIES

Conocybe microrrhiza Hauskn. var. **coprophila** Amandeep Kaur, Atri and Munruchi Kaur, Mycosphere 6(1): 29.2015 (BOLBITIACEAE).

Distribution: Chandwaja, Faridkot district of Punjab, India at 196m.

Scutellinia setosa var. **muscivorum** Konchok Dorje, Sanjeev Kumar and Yash Pal Sharma, Indian J. For. 38(2): 126.2015 (PYRONEMATAACEAE).

Distribution: Wanla area, Khaltse, Leh, Ladakh of Jammu Kashmir, India.

NEW DISTRIBUTIONAL RECORDS

Genera Records

Rugiboletus G. Wu & Zhu L. Yang (BOLETACEAE).

Distribution: North and East district of Sikkim, India.

Species Records

Agaricus halophilus Peck (AGARICACEAE)

Distribution: Dau Majra, Mohali, Punjab, India.

Agrocybe microspora Singer

Distribution: Bahadurgarh, Patiala, Punjab.

Clitocybe dilatata (Pers.) P. Karst. (TRICHOLOMATACEAE)

Distribution: Kamsar, Poonch district of Jammu & Kashmir, India.

Clitocybe hydrogramma (Bull.) P. Kumm. (TRICHOLOMATACEAE)

Distribution: Kamsar, Poonch district of Jammu & Kashmir, India.

Coltricia permollis Baltaza & Gibertoni

Distribution: Krishna Ghati, Poonch district of Jammu & Kashmir, India.

Conocybe albipes (G.H. Otth) Hauskn. (BOLBITIACEAE)

Distribution: Chhat Bir, Punjab, India at 251m. altitude.

Conocybe apala (Fr.: Fr.) Arnolds (BOLBITIACEAE)

Distribution: New Forest at Forest Research Institute, Dehradun, Uttarakhand, India at 668m.

Conocybe fuscimarginata (Murrill) Singer (BOLBITIACEAE)

Distribution: Balbehra, Punjab, India at 251m.

Conocybe lenticulospora Watling (BOLBITIACEAE)

Distribution: Lohatbaddi, Ludhiana, Punjab, India at 254m.

Conocybe leucopus (Kühner) Kühner & Watling (BOLBITIACEAE)

Distribution: Mudki, Ferozepur, Punjab, India at 182m.

- Conocybe moseri** Watling (BOLBITIACEAE)
Distribution: Ajitwal, Moga, Punjab, India at 217m.
- Conocybe subpubescens** P. D. Orton (BOLBITIACEAE)
Distribution: Jalota Dasuya, Hoshiarpur, Punjab, India at 295m.
- Coprinus cordisporus** T. Gibbs (AGARICACEAE)
Distribution: Satiana, Hoshiarpur districts of Punjab, India at 295m.
- Cortinarius salor** Fr., (CORTINARIACEAE)
Distribution: Shingba Rhododendron sanctuary, North district of Sikkim, India at 3252m.
- Cortinarius varicolor** (Pers.) Fr., (CORTINARIACEAE)
Distribution: Dombang and Samthang, North district of Sikkim, India at 2890m.
- Haplotrichum curtisii** (Berk.) Hol.-Jech., (BOTRYOBASIDIACEAE)
Distribution: Manali district of Himachal Pradesh, India.
- Helvella solitaria** P. Karst. (HELVELLACEAE)
Distribution: Deovan, Chakrata, Dehradun, Uttarakhand, India at 2638m.
- Heterobasidion perplexa** Ryv. (POLYPORACEAE)
Distribution: Mawphlang sacred grove and Mawlai forest in East Khasi Hills of Meghalaya at altitudes of 1900 m and 1430 m.
- Hygrocybe miniata** (Fr.) P. Kumm. (HYGROPHORACEAE)
Distribution: New Forest, Forest Research Institute, Dehradun, Uttarakhand, India at 672m.
- Hymenochaete damicornis** (Link.) Lev. (HYMENOGYAPHAETACEAE)
Distribution: Manjari, Andaman & Nicobar Island.
- Hymenochaete depallens** Berk. M. A. Curtis, (HYMENOGYAPHAETACEAE)
Distribution: M. G. National park, Andaman & Nicobar Island.
- Hymenochaete floridea** Berk. & Broome (HYMENOGYAPHAETACEAE)
Distribution: Ross Island, Andaman & Nicobar Island.
- Hymenochaete murina** Bers. (HYMENOGYAPHAETACEAE)
Distribution: Ross Island Andaman & Nicobar Island.
- Hymenochaete muroiana** Hino & Katumoto (HYMENOGYAPHAETACEAE)
Distribution: Rut Island Andaman & Nicobar Island.
- Hymenochaete ochromarginata** P. H. B. Talbot (HYMENOGYAPHAETACEAE)
Distribution: Manjari Andaman & Nicobar Island.
- Hymenochaete pellicula** Berk. & Broome (HYMENOGYAPHAETACEAE)
Distribution: Baratang, Andaman & Nicobar Island.
- Hymenochaete pinnatifida** Burt., (HYMENOGYAPHAETACEAE)
Distribution: M. G. National park, Andaman & Nicobar Island.
- Hymenochaete separabilis** (Dicks.) Lev., (HYMENOGYAPHAETACEAE)
Distribution: Baratang, Andaman & Nicobar Island.
- Hymenochaete unicolor** Berk. & M. A. Curtis (HYMENOGYAPHAETACEAE)
Distribution: Ross Island, Andaman & Nicobar Island.
- Hymenochaete vallata** G. Cunn. (HYMENOGYAPHAETACEAE)
Distribution: Mount Harriet, Andaman & Nicobar Island.
- Hymenochaete variegata** Bresadola (HYMENOGYAPHAETACEAE)
Distribution: Mount Harriet, Andaman & Nicobar Island.
- Hymenochaete villosa** (Lev.) Bres. (HYMENOGYAPHAETACEAE)
Distribution: Baratang, Andaman & Nicobar Island.

Inonotus lloydii (Cleb.) P.K. Buchanan & Ryv.
(HYMENOGYSAETACEAE)

Distribution: Ross Island, Andaman & Nicobar Island.

Meliola luzonensis Syd. (MELIOLACEAE)

Distribution: Pratapgad, Mahabaleshwar district of Maharashtra, India at 829m.

Meliola sideroxyli Stev. (MELIOLACEAE)

Distribution: Gonoshi forest, Mahabaleshwar district of Maharashtra, India at 690m.

Meliola ventiliginicola Hansf. (MELIOLACEAE)

Distribution: Maharashtra, India at 858m.

Panaeolus alcidis Moser (PSATHYRELLACEAE)

Distribution: Chak Fatehpur, Moga, Punjab, India at 217m.

Panaeolus castaneifolius (Murrill) A.H. Sm. (PSATHYRELLACEAE)

Distribution: Sangrur, Sikanderpura Punjab, India at 231m.

Panaeolus venezolanus Guzmán (PSATHYRELLACEAE)

Distribution: Panjgraean, Faridkot, Punjab, India at 196m.

Panaeolus tropicalis Oláh., (PSATHYRELLACEAE)

Distribution: Nainakut, Patiala, Punjab, India at 251m.

Phellinus arctostaphyli (Long) Niemelä. (HYMENOGYSAETACEAE)

Distribution: Dongarwadi, Harishchandragad and Lonavala of Pune district of Maharashtra India at 251m.

Phellinus cesatii (Bres.) Ryv. (HYMENOGYSAETACEAE)

Distribution: M. G. National Park, Andaman & Nicobar Island.

Phellinus crocatus (Fr.) Ryv. (HYMENOGYSAETACEAE)

Distribution: M. G. National Park, Andaman & Nicobar Island.

Phellinus longisetulosus Bond et. Herr. (HYMENOGYSAETACEAE)

Distribution: Rut Island, Andaman & Nicobar Island.

Phellinus membranaceus Wright et Blumenf. (HYMENOGYSAETACEAE)

Distribution: M. G. National Park, Andaman & Nicobar Island.

Phellinus minutiporus Bond et Herr. (HYMENOGYSAETACEAE)

Distribution: M. G. National Park, Andaman & Nicobar Island.

Phellinus orientalis Bond et Herr. (HYMENOGYSAETACEAE)

Distribution: Rut Island, Andaman & Nicobar Island.

Phellinus pseudopunctatus A. David, Dequatre & Fiasson (HYMENOGYSAETACEAE)

Distribution: M. G. National Park, Andaman & Nicobar Island.

Phellinus reichingeri (Bres.) Ryv. (HYMENOGYSAETACEAE)

Distribution: Rut Island, Andaman & Nicobar Island.

Phellinus resinaceus Kotl. Et Pouz. (HYMENOGYSAETACEAE)

Distribution: M. G. National Park, Andaman & Nicobar Island.

Phellinus rhytiphloeus (Mont.) Ryv. (HYMENOGYSAETACEAE)

Distribution: Ross Island, Andaman & Nicobar Island.

Phellinus rufitinctus (Berk. et Curt. :Cke.) Pat. (HYMENOGYSAETACEAE)

Distribution: Ross Island, Andaman & Nicobar Island.

Phellinus sanctigeorgii (Pat.) Ryv. (HYMENOGYSAETACEAE)

Distribution: M. G. National Park, Andaman & Nicobar Island.

Phellinus sanfordii (C.G. Lloyd) Ryvarden. (HYMENOGYSAETACEAE)

Distribution: Lonavala of Pune district of Maharashtra India at 251m.

Phellinus sonoreae Gilbertson (HYMENOCHEAETACEAE)

Distribution: Ross Island, Andaman & Nicobar Island.

Phellinus swieteniae (Murr.)Herr.et Bond. (HYMENOCHEAETACEAE)

Distribution: Manjari, Andaman & Nicobar Island.

Podoscypha petaloides (Berk.)Boidin., (MERULIACEAE)

Distribution: Lonawala-Dhak Bhairi Dhak of Pune district of Maharashtra India at 251m.

Psathyrella vanhermanii Smith (PSATHYRELLACEAE)

Distribution: Parol, Mohali, Punjab, India at 316m.

Psathyrella sphaerocystis Orton (PSATHYRELLACEAE)

Distribution: Balamgarh, Sangrur, Punjab, India at 216m.

Psathyrella flocculosa(Earle) A.H. Smith (PSATHYRELLACEAE)

Distribution: Naushehra, Sangrur, Punjab, India at 231m.

Rugiboletus brunneiporus G Wu & Zhu L. Yang (BOLETACEAE)

Distribution: North and east district of Sikkim, India.

VARIETAL RECORDS

Coprinus comatusvar. **caprimammillatus** Bogart. (AGARICACEAE)

Distribution: Patiala and Hoshiarpur districts of Punjab, India.

Panaeolus papilionaceus var. **parvisporus** Ew. Gerhardt., (PSATHYRELLACEAE)

Distribution: Dugni, Sangrur, Punjab, India at 231m.

Psathyrella kauffmaniivar. **kauffmanii** Smith., (PSATHYRELLACEAE)

Distribution: Loahgarh, Moga, Punjab, India at 217m.

ALGAE

New Species

Gomphonema doonensis B. Karthick, R. Nautiyal & J.P. Kociolek, Nova Hedwigia 144: 169. 2015. (BACILLARIOPHYCEAE)

Distribution: Nalota stream, Dehradun, Uttarakhand.

Gomphonema juetnerii B. Karthick, R. Nautiyal & J.P. Kociolek, Nova Hedwigia 144: 166. 2015. (BACILLARIOPHYCEAE)

Distribution: Nalota stream, Dehradun, Uttarakhand.

Lemanea manipurensis E.K. Ganesan, J.A. West, Zuccarello & J. Rout, Algae 30 (1): 3. 2015. (RHODOPHYCEAE)

Distribution: Chakpi river, Manipur.

Nitzschia kociolekii Alakananda, B. Karthick, J.C. Taylor & P.B. Hamilton, Phycological Research 63: 31. 2015. (BACILLARIOPHYCEAE)

Distribution: Buldana, Maharashtra at 563m.

Nitzschia tripudio Alakananda, B. Karthick, J.C. Taylor & P.B. Hamilton, Phycological Research 63: 33. 2015. (BACILLARIOPHYCEAE)

Distribution: Buldana, Maharashtra at 563m.

Rhoicosphenia gandhii E.W. Thomas, B. Karthick & Kociolek, Diatom Research 30(1):36.2015. (RHOICOSPHENIACEAE)

Distribution: Galteshwar, near Mahi River, Gujarat, India.

Rhoicosphenia indica E.W. Thomas, B. Karthick & Kociolek, Diatom Research 30(1):37.2015. (RHOICOSPHENIACEAE)

Distribution: Galteshwar, near Mahi River, Gujarat, India.

Thalassiosira sunderbana B. Samanta & P. Bhadury, Phycological Research 63 (2): 104. 2015. (BACILLARIOPHYCEAE)

Distribution: Chemaguri creek, Sundarban, West Bengal.

Trentepohlia sundarbanensis G.G. Satpati & R. Pal, Phycos 45 (1): 2. 2015. (CHLOROPHYCEAE)

Distribution: Cheramatla Island, Sundarban, West Bengal.

NEW DISTRIBUTIONAL RECORDS

Apatococcus lobatus (Chodat.) J.B. Petersen (CHLOROPHYCEAE)

Distribution: AJC Bose Indian Botanic Garden, Howrah, West Bengal.

Aphanocapsa incerta (Lemmerm.) Cornberg &

Komárek (CYANOPHYCEAE)

Distribution: Ganga river in Bihar.

Chamaesiphon amethystinus (Rostaf.) Lemmerm.
(CYANOPHYCEAE)

Distribution: West Kameng district of Arunachal Pradesh, India.

Chamaesiphon polonicus (Rostaf.) Hansg.
(CYANOPHYCEAE)

Distribution: Thongling stream in Tawang district of Arunachal Pradesh, India.

Chroococcopsis epiphytica Geitler
(CYANOPHYCEAE)

Distribution: Ganga river in Bihar.

Cosmarium ornatum Ralfs ex Ralfs
(CHLOROPHYCEAE)

Distribution: Ganga river in Bihar.

Encyonema subalpinum (Hustedt) D.G. Mann
(BACILLARIOPHYCEAE)

Distribution: Giri River, Dadahu, Himachal Pradesh.

Entomoneis alata (Ehrenb.) Ehrenb.
(BACCILARIOPHYCEAE)

Distribution: Ganga river in Bihar.

Euastrum verrucosum Ehrenb. ex Ralfs var.
reductum Nordst. (CHLOROPHYCEAE)

Distribution: Ganga River in Bihar.

Gomphonema towutense Hustedt (BACILLARIOPHYCEAE)

Distribution: Satluj river, Mandi, Himachal Pradesh.

Navicula parietina Kütz. (BACCILARIOPHYCEAE)

Distribution: Ganga River in Bihar.

Prasiolopsis ramosa Vischer (CHLOROPHYCEAE)

Distribution: Banjhakri waterfall, Gangtok, Sikkim.

Protoderma viridae Kütz. (CHLOROPHYCEAE)

Distribution: Gilai Sagar, Sawaimadhopur, Rajasthan.

Conclusion: Compilation of information on new discoveries within the political boundary of India was done like previous years from various sources and published journals. We thankfully acknowledge all the journal editors, and the authors for sharing these published works. (names of journals are given in the text). In the effort of this compilation, we received overwhelming support from all taxonomists across the country and even outside. This document, became a ready reckoner for not only botanists, researchers and teachers but also for policy makers and general people. It is also to bring the attention of all the researchers that, in spite of a good number of discoveries of taxa in recent years, type specimens of many of these newly described plant species have not been deposited in the herbarium indicated in the publication. Attention is further drawn to the subsection (3) of section 39 of the Biological Diversity Act, 2002 which stipulates that “*Any new taxon discovered by any person shall be notified to the repositories or institutions designated for this purpose and he shall deposit the voucher specimens with such repository or institution.*” Botanical Survey of India, as custodian of 02 million of plant specimens and as one of the designated repository can further help in facilitating taxonomic research in our country and stimulating taxonomic research and collaborative efforts not only in the country, but outside also.